

THE IMPORTANCE OF ULTRASONIC EXAMINATION IN PANCREATIC DISEASES.

**Aminov Shakhruh Khamdamjon ugli., Karimov Rasulbek Khasanovich.,
Aitimova Gulsanam Yusupovna.
Urgench State Medical Institute.**

Current relevance of the topic: In the field of medicine, pancreatic diseases are widespread in the practice of gastroenterology, and modern instrumental examination methods are of great importance for the early detection of this disease and differential diagnosis with other diseases. Also, today ultrasound examination (USG) is a non-invasive, safe, and widely used diagnostic method. Therefore, in scientific research, the diagnostic significance of ultrasound in the early detection of pancreatic diseases is analyzed.

Purpose of the work: to study the possibilities and clinical significance of ultrasound in the diagnosis of pancreatic diseases.

Research methods: During the conducted scientific work, ultrasound of the pancreas was performed on patients admitted to the hospital. During the examination, changes in the size, echogenicity, structure, and surrounding tissues of the pancreas were assessed. These identified data were compared with clinical and laboratory results.

Results obtained: as a result of ultrasound examination, it was observed that it is possible to identify acute and chronic pancreatitis of the pancreas, cystic changes of the pancreas, tumor processes, and destructive changes in the pancreas. In acute pancreatitis, an increase in the volume of the gland, a decrease in echogenicity, and a heterogeneous structure of the parenchyma were noted. In chronic pancreatitis, densification of the parenchyma, increased echogenicity, and dilation were detected. This examination method made it possible to identify morphological changes in the gland at an early stage.

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that ultrasound is an effective and reliable method for the early detection and diagnosis of pancreatic diseases. Its non-invasiveness, safety, and reusability ensure its widespread use in clinical practice. Therefore, it is advisable to use ultrasound examination as part of complex diagnostic studies in the detection of pancreatic pathologies.

References:

1. Айтимова, Г. Ю. (2017). Ультразвуковой скрининг заболеваний

периферических артерий. *Авиценна*, (12), 33-36.

2. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рузметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.

3. Юлдашев Б. С. и др. Хомила ва янги туғилган чақалоқлар мурдасининг суд тиббий экспертизаси (Текшируви) //Ўқув кўлланма: Т.:“О ‘ZKITOVSAVDONASHRIYOTI” NMIU. – 2023. – Т. 96.

4. Каримов, Р., Аллаберганов, Д., Джуманиязов, Р., Жуманиязов, М., & Матясубов, Ю. (2026). БОШ МИЯ ЁПИҚ ЖАРОХАТЛАРИДА ОШҚОЗОН ОСТИ БЕЗИНИНГ УЧРАШ ДАРАЖАСИ. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION RESEARCH CONFERENCE, 3(1), 26–27.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18391998>

5. Karimov, R., Allaberganov, D., Matyasubov, Y., Dzhumaniyazov, R., & Dzhumaniyazov, M. (2026). PATHOLOGICAL ANATOMY OF THE ADRENAL GLAND IN CLOSED BRAIN INJURIES. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCE, 3(2), 24–26.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18452434>

6. Karimov, R., Allaberganov, D., Jumaniyazov, M., Matyasubov, Y., & Jumaniyazov, R. (2026). PATHOLOGICAL ANATOMY OF THE THYROID GLAND IN WOMEN WITH CEREBRAL INJURIES. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES, 3(1), 37–39. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18453189>

7. Karimov, R., Allaberganov, D., Dzhumaniyazov, R., Dzhumaniyazov, M., & Matyasubov, Y. (2026). THE DEGREE OF INJURY OF THE PAPYRACUTUS IN CLOSED BRAIN INJURIES. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE, AND EDUCATION, 3(1), 93–95.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18452918>

8. Аминов, Ш., Каримов, Р., & Айтимова, Г. (2026). ОШҚОЗОН ОСТИ БЕЗИ КАСАЛЛИКЛАРИДА УЛЬТРОТОВУШ ТЕКШИРУВИНИНГ АХАМИЯТИ. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND SOCIAL-HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES, 3(2), 100–101.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19208251>